

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Loquet**FIRST NAME:** Wim**PROGRAM CODE:** MNRJ-R**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Office Home on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Do we have to cite someone else's work?

- Yes, we cite quotations, paraphrases and we add a list of works cited.¹**
- Yes, but we only use in-text citations when applying the Turabian style.
- No. All information is readily available online for everyone to see.
- No. It is not required when only using an idea or copy sentences of less than 1000 words.

Commented [GK1]: Why are all your correct answers the first in the multiple-choice? Try to shuffle them! Check footnote #1 below!

2. Which program do we use to add citations, which for bibliographies?

- Zotero for citations and bibliographies.²**
- Grammarly for citations, Zotero for bibliographies.
- Grammarly for bibliographies, Zotero for citations.
- Grammarly for citations and bibliographies.

3. What are the consecutive steps in writing?³

- Prewriting, drafting, revising, editing and publishing.**
- Drafting, revising, prewriting, publishing, and editing.
- Editing, revising, prewriting, drafting, and publishing.
- Drafting, prewriting, editing, publishing, and revising.

4. What do we do when we talk about proofreading?

- We verify punctuation, mechanics, spelling, choice of words, and understanding of sentences and language used in our work.⁴**
- We read our work before sending it out.

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Commented [GK2]: Since this source is cited in full above, you can use a shortened citation. See the affected footnote below!

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. 3rd ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), [insert page number here!](#).

² EUCLID, “Zotero Training - EUCLID University ACA-401 and ACA-401D” (video of lecture, Euclid University, August 29, 2017), accessed December 28, 2021, <https://vimeo.com/231577694>.

³ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning* (Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 15.

⁴ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, [400](#).

Deleted: *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning* (Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 400.

- We let someone read our work for us before sending it out.
- We read out loud to ensure it sounds good for an audience.

5. **What are the sequential steps we take towards writing a thesis?**

- Select a topic, find a question, propose a working hypothesis, build a storyboard to guide your work.**⁵
- Find a question you are sure you know the result of and fill in all the missing steps, ensuring that you do not deviate from your initial idea.
- Select a topic you like, then elaborate on the subject in great detail.
- Start early and collate all the info you can on an exciting topic.

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6. **How can we best present numbers in our work?**

- Table for values, chart for comparison, and graph for trends.**⁶
- Table for comparison, chart for trends, and graph for values
- Table for trends, chart for values, and graph for comparison.
- Any type of presenting is suitable, but do not use the same one too often.

7. **What do we mean by using a writing style?**

- Apply agreed on rules on punctuation, capitalisation, referencing, how to quote in-text, how to construct a bibliography, and so on.**⁷
- There are three styles: informative, entertaining, and scientific.
- Usage of fancy words to make the characters seen as elegant and chic.
- The font that we use for our text. Ideally, we use Arial, size 11.

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⁵ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 2nd ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 23-34.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 86.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian et al., [13](#).

Deleted: *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 2nd ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 13.

8. **Do we spell numbers out in words or numerals if our topic heavily relies on data (Turabian)?**

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- Spell out single-digit numbers. Write numerals for all others.**⁸
- Turabian style dictates spelling out all numbers for clarity.
- Turabian style requires us to write all in numerals for clarity.
- Only if the number uses more than five words, we use numerals.

9. **When must we provide a citation? (Most accurate answer)**

Only when we quote directly, paraphrase or use someone else's ideas, work, methods, tables, experiments, results, and so on.⁹

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- Only when we use the exact text as we found in our source.
- Only when we copy the text from our source with "Ctrl-C/Ctrl-V".
- Only when we quote or paraphrase from a printed book.

10. **What is the group name of Treaties and agreements regulating the EU?**

- Primary Legislation.**¹⁰
- Core Regulations (CR).
- European Regulations Book (ERB).
- Main Set of Treaties (MST).

⁸ Ibid., 340-341.

⁹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 3rd ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), [insert page number here](#).

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed. (Luxemburg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2020), 72.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.